

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES IN CHILDREN OF SCHOOL AGE

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Annotation: The article deals with the age characteristics of schoolchildren, the development of physical qualities and motor abilities of schoolchildren.

Key words: development of children's physical qualities, motor abilities, age characteristics, motor function.

Introduction. School age is the most favorable for the development of motor abilities, especially speed and coordination abilities to perform cyclic actions for a long time in the mode of moderate and high intensity [1, 2]. The development of motor abilities is carried out in two main directions - stimulating and directed. Stimulating development is carried out in the process of formation of motor skills and is associated with teaching children the basics of movement control. Directed development is manifested in an increase in the functional capabilities of the body and is ensured by performing well-mastered exercises under conditions of a change in the value of the training load [4, 5, 6].

Motor function is understood as a set of physical qualities, motor skills and abilities of children, adolescents and adults. At the same time, the motor function is one of the complex physiological phenomena that provide resistance to environmental conditions [7, 8, 9].

The fact that the most intensive improvement of the motor function of those involved occurs before the age of 13-14 is evidenced by the works of many authors [10, 11]. The formation of the motor analyzer of children is subject to the laws of age development and is carried out over a number of years. From 7 to 14 years old, there is an active development of the motor function of children and adolescents, which reaches a high level by the age of 13-14. Further development of the functions of the

sensory systems of the body is less intensive [12, 13]. Consequently, already by this age, the morphological and functional maturation of the human motor sensory system is basically completed.

The formation of motor function in children is determined not so much by the maturation of the musculoskeletal system, but by the degree of maturity of the higher centers of movement regulation [14, 15]. In the period between 7 and 11 years, the coordination of voluntary exercises in children improves significantly, movements become more diverse and accurate, acquire smoothness and harmony. Children of this age master the ability to dose their efforts, to subordinate movements to a certain rhythm, in the internal organs. Consequently, the level of development of physical qualities is directly dependent on the consistency of somatic and vegetative functions.

Physical qualities experience various influences of genetic factors in their development. The speed of movement, muscle strength and especially endurance are subject to strong control by the genotype.

Children's age is an important stage of long-term physical development and favorable for the start of sports training [16].

Based on the data of scientific and methodological literature, the development of physical qualities in schoolchildren has its own age-specific features: it occurs heterochronously, the size of annual gains is not the same in different age periods and differs in relative values when comparing the increase in motor qualities [17, 18]; in most children of primary and secondary school age, the indicators of physical qualities are different in their level (for example, the level of power static endurance, as a rule, does not coincide with the level of development of dynamic endurance) [19, 20]; special training, carried out by the same method with the same volume and intensity of physical activity, allows you to compare the data of children of different ages, gender, physical development, gives a different pedagogical effect - a higher level of development of physical qualities during a natural increase (sensitive period) in children, adolescents and young men who are not involved in sports; the level of

development of physical qualities at each age differs in those involved in various sports [21].

Consideration of age characteristics is important for the development and improvement of physical qualities in the process of functional training of schoolchildren at the initial stage.

At primary school age, there are favorable prerequisites for the development of speed of movements [22]. Correspondence of short-term high-speed loads with the functional capabilities of children is due to the high excitability of the innervation mechanisms that regulate the activity of the motor apparatus, the high mobility of the main nervous processes and the high intensity of metabolism inherent in the child's body.

Later than other physical qualities, endurance develops, which is characterized by the time during which a sufficient level of body performance is maintained. With age, endurance both with static efforts and with dynamic work increases markedly. In children of 6-13 years old, involved in sports, the development of the body occurs more intensively, therefore, functional changes at this age create favorable prerequisites for the development of motor qualities.

Features of the physical development of children of primary school age limit the use of strength exercises, children of this age are better able to tolerate loads of speed-strength impact: jumping exercises, acrobatic and dynamic exercises on gymnastic apparatus, and throwing are widely used.

Means of strength development should contribute to the improvement of the main muscle groups of the belt of the upper and lower extremities, the muscles of the body (back, chest and abdomen). The greatest effect in the development of strength abilities is obtained from exercises performed with maximum intensity, which allow you to comprehensively develop all muscle groups.

Speed abilities develop most successfully in early childhood and adolescence: during this period, it is advisable to cultivate speed by means that are aimed at

increasing the frequency of movements. At 11-14 years of age, speed abilities should be increased mainly through exercises of a speed-strength nature.

The development of speed is very effective when used in the classroom for sports and outdoor games. The ability to resist fatigue develops when, during training, the body of the practitioner is brought to fatigue.

Conclusion. Thus, static endurance can be developed from primary school age (although children do not have a high level of its development), using slow running lasting 8-30 minutes, sports games (football, rugby, handball) lasting 30-60 minutes, running with maximum intensity or outdoor games of the same orientation, slow running over rough terrain.

Consequently, the development of physical qualities in children and adolescents depends on two main factors: the age-related development of physiological systems and the mechanisms of their interaction and the training effect with regular physical activity.

References:

1. Karimovna, K. S. (2022, December). Development of performance skills of gymnasts in gymnastics. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 268-272).
2. Alikulovich M. K., & Yuldashevich T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(3).
3. Alikulovich M. K. (2022). Mobile Games on the Water as a Means of Developing the Physical Qualities of School Children. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 783–786.
4. Менгликулов, Х. (2022). 14-15 ёшдаги сузувчиларда тезлик-куч сифатларини ривожлантириш услубиёти. *Жамият ва инновациялар*, 3(6/S), 81–87.

5. Менгликулов, Х. А. (2020). Особенности физической подготовки специалистов физической культуры в высшем учебном заведении. *Педагогика ва психологияда инновациялар*, 11(3).
6. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022, October). The significance of psychological preparation of young swimmers. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 84-88).
7. Abdullaev Y. (2021). Forms and methods of developing the use of folk movement games in high school students. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(2), 73-79.
8. Abdullaev Yashnarzhon Makhkamovich. (2021). Physical education of senior schools by means of folk moving games. *European Scholar Journal*, 2(11), 70-72.
9. Абдуллаев Я. М., Турдимуродов Д. Й. Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов / Я. М. Абдуллаев, Д. Ю. Турдимуродов // *Colloquium-journal*. - 2020. -№ 24-2(76). -С. 14-16.
10. Abdullaev, Y. M., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Creation of pedagogical conditions in the formation of volitional grades in primary school students. *Colloquium-journal*.
11. Kh, K. B. (2019). Формирование чувства национальной гордости воспитанников начальных классов домов милосердия посредством хадисов. *International scientific review*, (LXIV), 54-56.
12. Каримова, Б. Х. (2019). Формирование национальной гордости у воспитанников 2 классов домов мехрибонлик на основе хадисов. In *European research: innovation in science, education and technology* (pp. 35-37).
13. Karimova, B. X. (2021). Mehribonlik uylari boshlang'ich sinf tarbiyalanuvchilarida milliy g'ururni hadislar asosida shakllantirishning nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(9), 952-961.

14. Турдимуратов, Д. Ю. Теория и методика настольного тенниса / Д. Ю. Турдимуратов. - Термез : Irfon-print, 2022. - 230 с.
15. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. *Problems and scientific solutions, Australia, Melbourne*.
16. Turdimurodov, D. (2022). Volitional qualities of a person and their formation in adolescent age. *Models and methods in modern science, 1(14)*, 13-17.
17. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2022, September). Formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. In *International scientific conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 198-204).
18. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education, 3(7)*, 283-289.
19. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Self-education of volitional qualities in children of senior school age. *International Journal of Pedagogics, 2(06)*, 34-39.
20. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Жисмоний тарбия дарси мактаб ўқувчиларида иродавий сифатларни ривожлантирувчи восита сифатида. *Общество и инновации, 3(6/S)*, 74-80.
21. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 3(03)*, 405-413.
22. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current research journal of pedagogics, 2(09)*, 47-51.